

CONTINUOUS TRAINING OF TEACHERS FOR THE USE OF DICT IN PRESENTIAL AND DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to show several TDICs for use in teaching and to raise awareness in teachers of the importance of continuing education. The methodology has an exploratory and participatory character and was carried out through the application of a hybrid course, where the following were worked: Videoconferencing platforms; Screen capture tools; Virtual Teaching and Learning Environments (AVEA); Platforms for interaction through games or polls; Science experiment simulators and collaborative applications. During the course, questionnaires were applied, the results of which indicated that: 100% did not know the resources worked; they are more confident and motivated to teach, as they now know resources to survey the students' prior knowledge on the subject, to carry out the assessment; working

with practical classes and using Quizzes; Kahoot was the most appreciated feature; the cell phone was considered by 100% of the participants as an indispensable tool for teaching. The results show that the course achieved its goals by being able to equip the teacher for the use of various technological resources, showing how to leave the traditional teaching method, for a method with more creative and dynamic classes, where the student becomes an active agent in the process.

Keywords: TDICs Teacher training. Remote teaching.

1. Introduction

Considering the impacts caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (CICCOZZI *et al.* , 2020), on education, and considering that continuing education must meet the reality in which teachers work, their needs, their anxieties, deficiencies and difficulties encountered at work , in order to be able to visualize, among other factors, technology as a necessary tool and actually use it consistently, raising the quality standards of teaching and education (Araújo *et al.* , 2020) it is *necessary* to necessary, continuing education courses for teachers in the area of technology applied to teaching.

When we talk about continuing teacher education, we are referring to complementary courses, aimed at active teachers, which should take place, as far as possible, in service, with the aim of helping educators to acquire new knowledge and thus be able to better perform their role. at school. This training should enable the construction, based on the challenges themselves, placing the teacher as the subject of the process, allowing the exchange of experiences, carrying out reflective dynamics and the construction of knowledge, characterized by a logic of action in which training and practice are intertwined. articulate for a real problem (SILVA & SANTOS, 2020).

Anjos (2008, p. 573) points out that “not knowing how to adjust the pedagogical use of new technologies means remaining traditional using new and emerging resources”. This provides an indication that the use of digital technologies in the classroom, without a clear purpose, will not make the class more stimulating; it is necessary to know how to work with them, pedagogically speaking.

Digital Information and Communication Technologies (TDICs) have great potential to be used in the educational context (Fontes *et al.* , 2021; Oscar *et al.* , 2021; Siqueira, 2018), as it has had a great impact on Education, enabling new forms of learning, dissemination of knowledge and especially, new relationships between teacher and student (FERREIRA, 2014, P. 15).

Due to their own characteristics, courses in the distance learning modality (EAD) have been using, for a long time, various technological resources in the teaching process. But courses in the face-to-face modality, much less. However, it is clear that from the 2020 school year onwards, which was very atypical due to the COVID-19 pandemic, educational institutions, in face-to-face form, had to invest in the use of technologies, which ensured that classes move from face-to-face to hybrid form, that is, classes without face-to-face contact, whose classes are synchronous (that is, at the same normal class time, transmitted simultaneously with technological resources, where the teacher interacts with the student) and with asynchronous activities (for the student to do later).

Faced with the emergency, in that period, many companies that work with the offer of technology aimed at the educational segment, put their most complete educational packages at zero cost, in order to help in teaching and publicize their product, providing educational tools capable of filming, record, share screen, hold meetings, chat, among other features. Liberal professionals in the area of technology and renowned professors also contributed by offering many courses, workshops, lectures in a hybrid format, with lives (live meetings transmitted over the internet) and recorded video lessons (to be consulted later).

It is indisputable that technology is a great ally in the teaching process, however, the lack of teacher training in the area makes many professionals resistant to the use and incorporation of new technologies in the classroom and stop using them. for lack of knowledge. This challenge must be faced by the teacher, as well as that of reflecting and rethinking their pedagogical practice (COSTA, 2015).

For this reason, firstly, for technology to be added to education, it is necessary for educators to appropriate knowledge, because even though teachers are aware of the importance of using technologies in the classroom, they still face the challenges of associating the pedagogical content with technological instruments, which reinforces the idea that a permanent search for teacher training is needed to develop skills and techniques necessary for truly meaningful learning (SILVA, PRATES & RIBEIRO, 2016), providing provide the teacher with critical training in relation to digital technologies, with a view to their pedagogical and intentional use in the school environment.

There are many TDICs available for different purposes in the educational context that allow, for example, to carry out synchronous hybrid classes, record classes, produce edited videos, explore practical activities through simulators or applications containing games and/or polls. In this article, we present some TDICs and their possibilities of use in teaching.

This research is directly linked to the aspirations of the authors of this article, as teachers, who make use of technological tools in their home and professional routine and who identify with the difficulties that teachers have faced in developing their teaching, where together they reflect on the strategies and methodologies adopted, such as the applicability of several TDICs for hybrid and face-to-face teaching.

2. Methodology

This work was carried out with participants of a university extension course, in a hybrid way, in which 50 vacancies were offered, with a workload of 60 hours, in the year 2020, whose registrations were carried out through Google forms , which *contained* questions that allowed identifying the profile and motivation of the participants.

Worked on: Videoconferencing platforms; Screen capture tools; Teaching and Learning Virtual Environments; Interaction platforms through games or polls; Science experiment simulators; Video Platforms and Collaborative Applications.

Each week different resources were worked on, and on Wednesdays the activities were asynchronous, whose guidelines were passed on through e-mails, forums and video-lessons and their scripts made available on AVEA Moodle ; on Thursdays, online (synchronous) orientations took place via Zoom, Meeting or Moodle (Big Blue Button), on this date activities involving Kahoot , Mentimeter *and* YouTube *were also carried out* ; on fridays, tasks were made available to students, which had a deadline of one week to complete them. These with the aim of optimizing learning and reminding the teacher of the importance of the task for the teaching-learning process.

As didactic strategies were worked, the flipped classroom and gamification, which were used in conjunction with digital tools (Mentimeter and Kahoot).

Kahoot was worked on in the form of quizzes. Participants were taught how the teacher and students joined the platform, how to set up their platform, how to use an existing one and how to share it, both as a task (challenge) and as a presentation.

The Mentimeter was used in the content presentation format through slides, in a playful way. Quizzes, interactive questions and tasks were also used. In addition, it was taught how to create a quiz in Mentimeter, how to use an existing one and how to share them.

Google documents were worked on so that the teacher could send and/or receive work, individual or collective, and share activities, lesson preparation, etc.

Google Forms were exploited for class activities, assignments, quizzes and assessments,

with time limiting and immediate feedback.

The jamboard, which is a virtual board, was designed so that the teacher could use it to correct exercises and present content in a collaborative way. It was explored via meet, classroom and drive, with access via notebook, tablet or smartphone.

For the teacher to record a complete class, he was taught how to use the screen capture and sharing tools (loom, screencastify, zoom and meet), explaining how to work with the use of power point slides, show videos, simulations, Quizzes , exercises, among others.

On YouTube, they were taught how to insert a video and generate the link; verify the security of video sources; search videos; create and make available playlists and important points about setting up live streams. As part of this module activity, participants searched for videos related to one of their disciplines and then created a public playlist of at least ten of those videos from three different channels.

The available PhET Colorado simulators were designed to indicate ways for the teacher to better explore the experiments, with the elaboration of scripts containing theoretical and calculation questions.

At the end of each subject, the participant applied it in their classroom and then presented the report.

The activities were planned, considering the heterogeneous public. For this reason, during the performance of each activity, we tried to highlight how to use the resources both via notebook and via smartphone, with access via links in the Moodle and Classroom virtual environments.

3. Results and discussion

Enrollment closes on the first day of enrollment for the course. Indicating that teachers were looking for instructions to work remotely. It is important to inform that the activity took place in a city in the interior of Paraná, where courses in this area are rarely offered. Of those enrolled, 26 completed the course completely, 4 partially, as they did not carry out all the activities, and 20 did not start the course.

The issue of evasion/withdrawal in distance courses is not new and has been noticed in several courses. According to Almeida (2008), the reasons can be classified into five categories: situational factors; lack of academic support; problems with technology; lack of administrative support and work overload.

The research carried out by Martins *et al .*, (2011), in the regions of Brazil, indicated

that, in the southern region (which is the region where we developed this research), cases of withdrawal from online courses are due to: personal problems (29%) and professionals (29%), followed by lack of time to attend the course (28%) and, to a lesser extent, problems related to the local infrastructure for accessing the internet (14%).

The aforementioned lack of time was also felt by all course participants, as, during the pandemic, information arrived via emails, WhatsApp, meetings and had to be passed on in the same way, via virtual environments, as we were in a period of social distancing. In this way, the speed provided by technology for receiving and disseminating information overloaded everyone, especially those who had no affinity with the use of various technological resources in teaching, which demanded more time.

The profile of subscribers was identified after registration, via the Google form. That This information was very important for planning the course, the analysis of which provided some indications:

(1) in relation to the area of expertise of the participants, likewise, 3.3% of those enrolled are from the areas of Amplifiers, History, Physical Education, Resistance of Materials, Medical Engineering, Geology, Biochemical Engineering, Administration, Sciences and Geography, 13.3% also work in Mathematics and Chemistry, 23.3% are in the field of Physics and 13.3% do not yet work as teachers, with 10% graduating in Chemistry and 3.3% doctoral students in Science. This information indicated that teachers from different areas of activity are having difficulties in using DICT applied to teaching.

(2) in terms of location, participants are distributed among the cities of Campo Mourão (70%), Goioerê (6.7%), São Pedro do Iguazu (6.7%), Maringá (6.7%), Assis Chateaubriand (3.3%), Pitanga (3.3%) and Jesuítas (3.3%). Having this result indicated that teachers from different locations in the interior of Paraná face the same difficulty.

(3) in relation to the motivation for participating in the course, all professors and students linked to the teaching area said that they intend to appropriate the TDICs to apply them in their work.

(4) 100% of the participants had never taught hybrid/EaD classes, but at that moment, 46% were teaching and the other 54% would soon start.

(5) Among the most used technological resources, the internet stands out, used both for searches and for playing videos, most of which were small films about the content that were displayed using the TV pendrive. An outdated practice, but one that is still present in the classrooms of public schools in the interior of Paraná.

(6) When asked about how they were preparing for the remote classes, at the beginning

of the social distancing period, the results indicated that: 2.2% of the participants dedicated themselves to reading about Microsoft Teams, Leadership, Arduino, Active Presenter , Open Shot, Gamification and Google Forms, and watched videos about DICTs; 4.4% dedicated themselves to learning about online tools, such as podcasts, Google tools and workshops offered by the Secretary of State for Education (SEED); 6.7% dedicated themselves to learning about active methodologies, teaching resources and advanced Moodle; 8.8% learning to use Google Classroom; 11.1% participated in workshops on video editing in the OBS Studio program (workshop given by the author SANTOS, OR), on basic Moodle (workshop given by the author FONTES, A.S) and on how to use Google Meet.

Analyzing the responses, we realized that all participants dedicated themselves to learning how to use digital technologies in the classroom, and most digital resources can be used both in a regular teaching environment and in the distance mode.

Through the responses of the participants, it is concluded that the knowledge of digital information and communication technologies, as well as the mastery of these technologies, became urgent at the time of social distancing, as teachers had to enter remote teaching, abruptly, emerging from this way, the need to know about digital resources for a better use of such technologies in the classroom.

From the analysis of the discussions carried out during the course, it was identified that, with so many resources available, what the teacher seeks is a tool that he can use promptly, that is practical, easily accessible and manipulated by the parties involved; that it is free and that the student can use, preferably, by smartphone.

The smartphone, which is a device full of technology and that people do not leave home without it, has become essential for teaching, as it allows *Audience Response System -ARS* activities to be carried out (Tereso *et al .*, 2019), which are interaction activities, in real time, which has provided an increase in students' attendance, involvement and attention, in response to stimuli presented by the teacher (Ludvigsen *et al.*, 2015). This, combined with the use of technological teaching resources, help teachers in the individual follow-up of students, enabling the verification of possible weaknesses in the face of activities that are carried out in the teaching-learning process.

In addition to the motivation presented in each text/activity, the display provided in all topics worked on in the AVEA, facilitated the organization of students in front of the platform, understanding that Moodle was unknown to a large part of those enrolled in the course, this being a platform versatile, which allows, in addition to inserting the teacher's material (slides, files, videos, simulations, etc.), interaction between teacher and students.

Figure 1 – How the tasks are passed on, via the forum, in Moodle, in order to motivate the participant.

Source: Authors' collection

There was active participation of student-teachers at all times during the course. This is reflected in the fact that constant monitoring was carried out by the coordinating professor of the course and author of this work, where, in addition to the course schedule, group and individual consultations were carried out to resolve any doubts, in addition, all On Wednesdays, new study topics were posted on the Moodle virtual environment, and all student-teachers accessed the material available on the platform, watching recorded classes on the use of different digital technologies. On Thursdays, they actively participated in online orientations via the Big Blue Button. On Fridays, tasks were posted, which all participants performed with dedication and quality. The activities developed during the course were monitored by the course coordinator-teacher via Moodle.

According to MARTINIANO & Rocha, (2014), it is used as an educational platform, mediated by teaching action, capable of promoting critical, creative and dialogical action by teachers and students.

All the requested tasks were based on the subject that the participant taught, so that he really learned how to use the resource in his classes and had his material ready to apply in the classroom.

Some of the TDICS presented, such as Kahoot, Moodle, Google Forms and Google Documents, have the possibility of providing immediate feedback-to the user. This information is very important, as the student, by quickly getting the answers back, is able to discern whether he is following the right path. In addition, even if distant from the teacher, interaction with him is possible in the development of each of the proposed activities. From this perspective, Anjos

(2008, p.573) argues, based on Bianchetti and Ferreira (2005), that “the interactivity between teacher and student is a possibility of building significant knowledge that can occur collectively”.

Therefore, it is up to the teacher to mediate the process of collective construction of knowledge. As Medeiros and Medeiros (2002, p.84) point out, although digital technologies are available to anyone, “there is no doubt that learning in interaction with human beings, with a real teacher, is an indispensable need”.

According to the last questionnaire, which served to verify the knowledge of the participants about the technologies worked on, as well as to evaluate the course and applied at the end of the course, via Google Forms, Kahoot was the resource that the participants most liked to work with, among the factors, the following stand out: It promotes good interaction with students; it is easy to access and manipulate; it can be explored at all levels of education and for any subject; it makes it possible to raise students' prior knowledge on a given subject and check whether there were signs of learning.

The questionnaire also indicated that the participants were delighted with the possibilities of creating and presenting slides in Kahoot and Mentimeter, which allow the insertion of short clips and music while students access the game, encouraging participants. However, the free version is very limited; in the option to assemble the slides as a 'task' the tool does not allow sending questions in the form of a quiz. Because of this, most participants reported that they would only use the mentimeter in face-to-face classes and the Kahoot, in both ways.

In the course, several possibilities for using Google Documents were explored, such as editing and sharing texts, monitoring and observations that can be made by the teacher, in work proposed to students, and tasks and assessments with time control. With this collaborative feature, it is possible to create, edit, share and print files in real time, using a computer, smartphone or tablet with anyone who has a Google account. It is a great option to monitor the development of student work.

The participants showed great satisfaction in relation to the possibilities (individual and group work, classes, assessments, etc.) of using google forms and docs, which make it possible to use them on the notebook, as well as on the smartphone. According to the participants, they reported that they intend to use both resources in their remote and face-to-face classes.

As a task related to the Google Forms topic, participants were asked to create an activity for their students, in which they should insert a video (extracted from YouTube), explaining the exposed content; a detailed text, with the description of the proposed activity. This activity

should contain: scoring, *feedback* and, optionally, a timer. The teachers were dazzled, because, although some already knew about the resource, they were not aware of the different possibilities of exploring it, especially with regard to the evaluation.

According to the students, “*the Jamboard saved us!*”, as they all missed having a board to write and correct the exercises. Figure 2 shows a task performed in the Mathematics discipline by participant M.

Figure 2 – Material prepared by participant M, on the jamboard.

Source: Authors' collection

It can be seen in figure 2 that the virtual jamboard allows the resolution of examples/exercises by the teacher and by the students as well, with a high degree of quality.

In all tasks, students posted on the VLE so that all participants had access and would make comments/suggestions on at least 2 other works. In this way, they contributed to the enrichment of their colleague's work, in addition to getting to know the work.

The questionnaire indicated that the teachers of the Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry and Science disciplines did not use simulators in their practical classes, because they did not know or did not know how to explore them, which is why they were amazed during the exploration of the resource, when they got to know the possibilities of use from the OVA of the PhET Colorado simulators, who learned how to prepare a script, explore the simulation and consult the lesson plan available on the Phet page.

The content presented on *YouTube* was able to motivate participants to use the platform, not only as consumers, but also as content producers, where 100% did not have this experience. For Moran (2013), videos serve to arouse students' curiosity about the subject and to illustrate content that is difficult to understand, helping to contextualize and bring the object of study closer to their realities. The result was very satisfactory, as the activities were sent and several students were able to produce their videos, this being their first time.

In the answers given by the participants in the questionnaire, it can be reported that they really enjoyed learning how to handle screen recording and sharing tools, such as *ScreenCastify* and *Loom*. To them, this seemed like a very distant thing to do; however, after the course, they

realized that these two features are very accessible. All participants were able to record an activity for their students, which was the task applied to this topic.

In relation to the concomitant training at work, the participants indicated that: 36.4% noticed that their students are more participative, since the classes involve technological resources; 27.3% realized that their students do not feel motivated, as they cannot dedicate themselves to their studies if there is no presence, or even pressure, from the teacher; 18.2% of teachers indicated that there is little participation of public school students in remote teaching and, therefore, they would not be able to observe changes in their classes; 9.1% indicated that student participation remains the same and 9.1% of teachers took over the class at this time, not being possible to observe any evidence of student motivation.

At that moment when the teacher seeks to adapt to an emergency teaching model, training himself to make the classes more attractive to the students, as well as to give continuity to the classes, it is important that the student also leave his comfort zone and try a little harder to learn. In line with Pazzini & Campos, (2020), student learning has always been one of the great challenges of teaching, where it is expected that the student has a greater participation in the process, in an interactive and active way.

When asked how they feel about returning to classes remotely, the results of the participants' responses indicated that 3.8% of them felt safe, 50% felt excited and 46.2% felt a little insecure, however, more prepared than at the beginning of the course. That is, most claim to be prepared, safe and excited for the development of teaching activities in the remote modality.

When asked about how this course can contribute to their teaching practice, all responses were very motivating and positive, with emphasis on:

“Just knowing these tools and their possibilities of use broadens our horizon of possibilities to offer the student quality and diversified content.” (Participant A).

“I believe that this course was very important to start learning about new technologies. Until then, I was unaware of the vast majority of resources presented during the course, and I was very satisfied with the approach taken. I will certainly go deeper and seek even more knowledge and practice with these technologies” (Participant B).

It is noticed in the speech of participant A a greater security and motivation to teach. In the speech of participant B, it is noted that the course was very productive and, still, would have awakened in him the desire to seek more depth in the area, in order to improve their teaching practice, making them more autonomous and critical after the appropriation of this knowledge. Corroborating the research by Silva, Prates & Ribeiro (2016), it appears that although the

teacher is aware of the importance of using new technologies in the classroom, he is still faced with the challenges of associating the pedagogical content with the technological instruments, which reinforces the idea that a permanent search for teacher training is needed to develop skills and techniques necessary for learning that is truly meaningful with the use of digital technologies in the classroom.

When asked about the importance of TDICs for teaching, especially in this pandemic period, the answers were very interesting, with emphasis on:

TDICS are important for teaching and learning, as they make teaching more dynamic and attractive for students. The student has the possibility of reviewing the contents worked on, in the case of video classes, interacting with the teacher either in a synchronous class or with tools such as the mentimeter, the kahoot, and the forms that help the teacher to verify the student's learning. In this period of social isolation, TDICS are tools that enable the continuity of teaching and learning, without which the process would be much more complicated and, in some cases, even impossible (Participant C).

The use of technological resources has been gaining prominence in the educational environment. Its use in the classroom allows the teacher to move away from the traditional teaching model and assume a role of mediator in the construction of the student's knowledge, and for that the teacher must be confident in the use of the various TDIC, which to accompany this advance, need to train themselves so as not to stick with their outdated methodology, because, given the knowledge of the students, they will be discouraged if the teacher does not prepare a class that uses these new technologies as a tool (Silva, Prates & Ribeiro, 2016).

4. Final considerations

The objective of the course was achieved, which was to equip teachers with the use of technologies in teaching, increasing their productivity, optimizing time and making classes more dynamic and productive, contributing to the insertion and use of digital technologies in the school environment. Some had many initial difficulties, which were resolved during the course, with the familiarization of resources.

Most participants were surprised by the potential of these tools and were very receptive to new technologies, which contributed to participants preparing their own materials, inserted in a VLE.

It was found that the activities provided the research subjects with moments of motivation, learning and reflections on their teaching practice and on new teaching possibilities. They experienced positive emotions linked to joy, enthusiasm, pride, gratitude and the

satisfaction of knowing and applying technologies for teaching, as these bring benefits at a personal and professional level, with the possibility of editing, copying, sharing, providing an optimization the time of application of the activity, reuse of activities for other classes, among others.

In addition, the use of technologies in the school environment, allows the skills previously brought by the students to be used in the classroom, promoting a dialogue between the previous knowledge of these students (regarding the use of technology) and the scientific knowledge presented by the proposed practice.

It was noticed the lack of knowledge, on the part of professors and undergraduates, in the use of specific technology for each teaching purpose, and the importance of continuing education for professors was recognized, especially in the area of TDICs; as well as the importance of inserting disciplines that address the use of digital technologies for initial training courses (license degree), as this is how integration in the educational process takes place, uniting technology, social and digital inclusion, as at all times there are new resources, new technologies and, like the teachers, everyone involved with the educational segment, must be prepared to follow these evolutions, as they are co-responsible for a dignified education, contextualized with the times in which we live. And above all, it is necessary for the institution to provide conditions for teachers to have digital resources available to diversify their classes and attract students.

5. References

ALMEIDA, OCS Evasion in distance courses: analysis of the reasons for dropping out. Research Report. ABED. São Paulo, 2008. Available at:

<http://www.abed.org.br/congresso2008/cd/artigos/552008112738PM.pdf> Accessed on 05/23/2022 .

ANJOS, AJS New technologies and the use of telematic resources in science education: computer simulation in physics education. **Brazilian Notebook for Teaching Physics** , v. 25, no. 3:p. 569-600, Dec. 2008.

ARAUJO, AN; PINTO, FS; MARTINS, TRB; BARBOSA, JRA The importance of continuing education in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. **Brazilian Journal of Development** , Curitiba, v.7, n.6, p. 55024-55031, Jun. 2021 Available at:

<https://www.brazilianjournals.com/index.php/BRJD/article/view/30783/pdf> Accessed on 05/24/2022.

COSTA, SM The influence of technological resources in the teaching-learning process. 2014. 43f. Completion of course work (Specialization in Fundamentals of Education):

Interdisciplinary Pedagogical Practices) - State University of Paraíba, Sousa, PB, 2014.

FERREIRA, MJMA New technologies in the classroom. Monograph of the Specialization Course in Fundamentals of Education: Interdisciplinary Pedagogical Practices. State University of Paraíba, Dean of Secondary, Technical and Distance Education, Department of PROEAD, Sousa, PB, 2014.

SOURCES, AS; COSTA, EF; SILVA, D. F; SANTOS, OR Contributions to teaching: Moodle Platform. **Teacher Training** , v. 13, n. 2:p. 87-104, 2021.

Ludvigsen, K., Krumsvik, R., & Furnes, B. (2015). Creating Formative Feedback Spaces in Large Lectures. **Computers & Education** , 88, 48-63, 2015. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0360131515001013> Accessed on 5/23/2022.

MARTINIANO, E.; ROCHA, ZFDC Production and availability of a biology didactic unit on the Moodle platform. In: **Innovative didactic proposal: ICT in science teaching**. ANDRADE, MABS & ROCHA, ZFD C 1st. Ed. Maringá: Massoni, 2014.

MARTINS, S.; MARTINS, C.; GIROTO, C.; POKER, R.; MILANEZ, S.; LIPPE, E. Specialized Educational Assistance: analysis of the evasion rate of professors in postgraduate courses, in the distance modality. **Indagatio Didactica** , vol. 3(2), June 2011. Available at: <https://repositorio.unesp.br/bitstream/handle/11449/115352/ISSN16473582-2011-03-02-203-216.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> Accessed at 05/23/2022.

MEDEIROS A.; MEDEIROS CF Possibilities and limitations of computer simulations in Physics teaching. **Brazilian Journal of Physics Teaching** , v. 24, no. 2, Jun./2002.

PAZZINI, LHS; CAMPOS, GHB The learning route: Would games be a path? Cap. 9, in **Série Educar** - Volume 4 – Technology/ Organization: Editora Poisson Belo Horizonte–MG: Poisson, 2020. Available online at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gilda_Campos/publication/339034954_A_rota_da_aprendizagem_Seriam_os_games_uma_via/links/5e6627a5299bf1744f6ba9d0/The-route-of-learning-would-be-the-games-a-way.pdf#page=56 Accessed on 20 Jul. 2020.

SILVA, CMB; SANTOS, EO Continuing training of integrated high school teachers: concepts and importance. **Brazilian magazine of professional and technological education**. V.1, p.1-15, 2020. Available at: <https://www2.ifrn.edu.br/ojs/index.php/RBEPT/article/view/9281/pdf> Accessed on: 05/24/2022 .

SILVA, ICS; PRATES, TS; RIBEIRO, LFS The New Technologies and learning: challenges faced by the teacher in the classroom. **Em Debate Magazine** (UFSC), Florianópolis, volume 16, p. 107-123, 2016. Available at: <https://periodicos.ufsc.br/index.php/emdebate/article/view/1980-3532.2016n15p107> Accessed on 05/18/2022.

SIQUEIRA, CCD Domain of digital technologies: essential competence for the 21st century teacher. Brasil Escola Electronic Portal [2018]. My article. Available at: <https://meuartigo.brasilecola.uol.com.br/educacao/dominio-das-tecnologias-digitais-competencia-indispensavel-professor-seculo-xxi.htm> Accessed on 09/05/2022.

TERESO, A.; MOURA, C.; SIMÕES, C.; AGUIAR, C.; SIARESM F.; MINA, I.; SILVA, J.; CAMPOS, J.; PEIXOTO, L.; ESCADAS, M.; AZEVEDO, M.; FORJAZ, M.; TRIGUEIROS, P.; OLIVEIRA, R.; ARAÚJO, S. Audience Response Systems as an instrument of innovation in teaching and active learning: Applications within a Community of Practice and Innovation in Teaching and Learning and students' perceptions. **CNaPPES 19 – ARS**. [DBio - Comunicações/Communications in Congresses](#), 2019.

Available at: http://repositorium.uminho.pt/bitstream/1822/73200/1/CNaPPES%2019%20-%20ARS_final.pdf Accessed on 05/23/2022.